

35 Shuffle

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Making a decision on a preferred option while minimizing the impact of self-interest or personal preference. It allows for making a democratic decision assessing different possibilities.

Benefits

This enhances democratic and joint decision-making in a project proposal consortium. It ensures that as many as possible options and viewpoints are considered by the entire group. This can be done in an offline and online setting.

Practical recommendations

Introduction (10 min)

Identify the question to which you want to explore the different options, preferences or viewpoints in the consortium.

Ask each person in the group to write their preferred option down on a card. The facilitator should check whether all options are unique. In case of duplicates: either ask the person to write another option or just remove the duplicate.

Round 1 – Card shuffle (2 min)

Each person gives their card to someone else. Each person should have now one card, which they will hold onto for the remainder of the exercise.

Round 2 – Scoring the options (+/-15 min, depending on the size of the group)

Each person now reads the option on this new card and gives it a score from 0 to 10, where 0 = 'I completely dislike this option' and 10 = 'I think this is the absolute best option'.

Each person now gets the opportunity to ask every participant to score the option on the card in their hands.

Round 3 – Comparing scores and group discussion (20 min)

Per option card, the average scores can now be calculated. Write this score prominently on the card. The facilitator can now rank the options from lowest to highest. The group can now enter a discussion about the options: are the highest scoring options indeed the most preferable? Why (not)?

Round 4 – Making a decision (5 min)

To finalise the session, the group should consolidate their final decision on which option they decide to go with or whether there is a need on further discussion.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Working with a diversity of backgrounds

Transparent communication about agendas, expectations and results

Promote a safe, open and cohesive culture

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[35 Shuffle technique](#)

*right click to open

Credit: The 35 Shuffle was sourced from the Integrated Research Toolkit (<https://integrated.landcareresearch.co.nz/>)

